

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Checklist for responsible research assessment

Full resource

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Introduction

Summary

The checklist for responsible assessment is a self-evaluation resource for exploring the whole assessment process in detail. The purpose is to make sure that the principles of responsible assessment are followed in an assessment process (Tatum et al. 2024).

The checklist is based on the Self-Evaluation Tool For Culture Of Open Scholarship Services by the Open Science Coordination in Finland, Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (Responsible Research series 15:2022, <https://doi.org/10.23847/tsv.447>).

The checklist is primarily designed for the purposes of **researcher assessment** but it can be also used for research assessment for applicable parts.

The checklist has been divided into five sections:

1. **Building the assessment process**, which is about e.g., values and purpose of the assessment process, and selecting the evaluators and data sources.
2. **Assessing the contribution to knowledge**, which is about e.g., context and use of research metrics.
3. **The diversity of research outputs and activities**, which aims to make sure that all relevant outputs and activities are taken into account in the evaluation.
4. **After the assessment** is about the steps to be taken immediately after the assessment, such as making sure that all parties know how the assessment process is proceeding and how to address potential concerns.
5. **Assessment of the assessment process** is a section for deeper self-reflection about the assessment process.

Checklist as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aims to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to OS. Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this checklist supports the application of the responsible assessment principles along the whole assessment process.

[SCOPE framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This checklist is relevant for all SCOPE stages.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Checklist

Tips for using the checklist:

- The checklist is meant primarily for the parties in charge of the planning and organising the assessment process.
- The checklist is meant to be used as a tool for self-assessment.
- The checklist is primarily designed for the purposes of **researcher assessment** but it can be also used for research assessment for applicable parts.
- Please note that since the purpose, level, available data etc. of the assessment vary, all points are not relevant for all assessment situations.
- Points that are not relevant for the current assessment event can be marked as not applicable by checking the N/A column.

1. Building the assessment process

Values, purpose, objectives and criteria	(✓)	N/A
Is the assessment based on what is valued, as discussed in, e.g., organisation's strategy, visions, policies or a value statement? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Value statement template https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524532 .		
Is the purpose of the assessment in line with the values? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Purpose and context statement template https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525469		
Are the objectives, guidelines, purpose and criteria of the assessment openly available to all parties?		
Are the objectives and criteria formulated in line with the values and purposes?		
Are the objectives and criteria formulated according to the generally recognised principles of responsible research(er) assessment (e.g., CoARA)?		
Has it been determined how the different aspects of research and innovation are weighed in relation to the purpose of the assessment?		
Selecting the evaluators	(✓)	N/A
Has it been ensured that there is no conflict of interest between evaluators and the subjects of assessment?		
Has it been ensured that the evaluators have the necessary substantive competence in the field/discipline?		
Has it been ensured that the evaluators have the necessary knowledge of the assessment process's objectives and methods, as well as the principles and practices of responsible assessment? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025		
Has the group of evaluators been selected so that it is sufficiently diverse in terms of, e.g., expertise, gender, geographical location, language and career-stage? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide for		

<p>assembling an assessment team https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525548</p>		
<p>Materials, data, methods and guidelines</p>	(✓)	N/A
<p>Are all the documents and information requested from the subjects of assessment relevant to the purpose of the assessment?</p>		
<p>Is there an opportunity for the subjects of assessment to present their views on the objectives, significance and impact of their work in the form of, e.g., narrative CV or a self-assessment report? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987</p>		
<p>Have the subjects of assessment been given clear instructions for submitting the material used in the assessment?</p>		
<p>Are there comprehensive guidelines for the evaluators defining the purpose of the evaluation, the objectives, the utilisation of results, the material and how it should be evaluated, and the content of the report they are expected to produce?</p>		
<p>Have the Terms of Reference (e.g., instructions on how to interpret the documents and information, such as narratives, indicators, bibliometrics, related to the assessment, and what kind of report is expected) been communicated to the evaluators well in advance of the start of the assessment?</p>		
<p>Do the subjects of the assessment know what material and documents are used in their assessment and that they have the right to check information concerning themselves?</p>		
<p>Have the subjects of assessment been required to give their permission to conduct e.g., bibliometric analysis?</p>		
<p>Is the assessment process transparent to all the parties?</p>		
<p>Is the progress of the assessment process communicated to all the parties throughout the process?</p>		
<p>Have the restrictions imposed by the data, materials and methods used been taken into account?</p>		
<p>Has it been ensured during the selection of criteria, methods, evaluation materials and experts that the selection is not discriminatory? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122</p>		

Have the discipline specific questions, e.g., publishing traditions, been taken into account?		
Have the different terms and criteria used in the assessment, e.g., the meaning of societal interaction and impact of research been clearly determined?		
Have the subjects of assessment been evaluated e.g., as a representative of their specific field(s), their career stage or organisation type and size?		
Have the subjects of assessment been evaluated in relation to the purpose of the current assessment?		

2. Assessing the contribution to knowledge

Assessment methods and context	(✓)	N/A
Is the assessment relying on qualitative judgement supported by responsibly used quantitative indicators where appropriate? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168		
Is it clear that indicators such as the Journal Impact Factor (JIF), Article Influence Score (AIS) and h-index should not be used as proxies for research quality and impact?		
Is it clear that the assessment is not based on university rankings?		
Is it clear that the language of the publication should not be used as a measurement of research quality?		
Have differences in disciplines and multidisciplinary aspects been taken into account in the evaluation?		
Publication and research metrics	(✓)	N/A
Is relevant expertise in publication metrics used for producing, using and interpreting quantitative evaluation?		
Are the constraints and lacks of the quantitative data on knowledge contributions used understood and described?		
Has the use of data and analysing methods, e.g., database, time-window and indicators, used to produce the analyses been as open and transparent as possible?		

Has it been possible for the subjects of the assessment to check and verify the data used as the basis for the bibliometric analysis and the results of the analysis?		
Have the publication indicators used in the assessment been selected so that they are relevant to the purpose of the assessment?		
Have the results been reported with the accuracy of the indicator values relevant to the subject, methodology and data of the assessment?		
Have the assessment reports clearly indicated the role of metrics in the overall assessment process?		

3. The diversity of research outputs and activities

	(√)	N/A
Research and innovation		
Have all relevant research outputs of different formats and types – including but not limited to, e.g. publications, data, methods – and in different languages been taken into account extensively in the assessment?		
Have the subjects of assessment’s input in relevant tasks, e.g., role in conducting of research, been taken into account in the assessment as an important part of their work?		
Have the subjects of assessment’s activities to promote open science and responsible research taken into account as part of the assessment? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526089		
Has the implementation of the ethical principles of research been taken into account in the assessment process?		
	(√)	N/A
Teaching and supervision		
Have the subjects of assessment’s teaching and supervision tasks and the competence and merits accumulated in these been taken into account in the assessment as an important part of their work?		
Have the different opportunities for teaching and supervision tasks been taken into account in the assessment as an important part of their work?		

Leadership and service	(✓)	N/A
Have the subjects of assessment's leadership and service tasks – e.g., leading a research project, contributing to editorial work – and the competence and merits accumulated in these been taken into account in the assessment as an important part of their work?		
Societal interaction	(✓)	N/A
Has subjects of assessment's societal interaction been taken into account in the assessment as an important part of their work?		

4. After the assessment

	(✓)	N/A
Has the progress of the assessment process been communicated to the subjects of assessment at all the relevant stages?		
Has the assessment been planned in a manner that allows the subjects of assessment also to benefit from it, e.g., in the form of feedback?		
Was feedback from all the relevant parties, e.g., evaluators and subjects of assessment, required? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Stakeholder mapping template https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686		
Have the subjects of assessment been informed who to contact if they have questions or concerns about the assessment process?		
Have GDPR guidelines been followed for the storage and disposal of sensitive documents related to research assessment?		

5. Assessment of the assessment process

	(✓)	N/A
Have the selected criteria been consistently followed throughout the assessment process? Please see the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide for evaluating the assessment process https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526189		
Have the steps and decisions of the assessment with their reasoning been documented?		
Was the progress of the assessment process communicated to the subjects of assessment throughout the process?		

Were the outcome of the assessment process and the reasoning leading to that clearly communicated to the subjects of assessment?		
If feedback from the process was received, was it handled and used to improve the future assessment processes?		
Have the experiences and lessons learned been used for mutual learning, e.g., between institutions?		

References

International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report.

<https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

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